

EJP SOIL
ARTEMIS

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

ARTEMIS

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Soil is critically linked to a multitude of ecosystem services, and the capacity to do so is strongly influenced the type of applied land use. Agroecological practices employ promising methods that potentially can contribute to mitigate or abate climate change, yet knowledge on their effectiveness is still patchy. This report summarises the outcomes of the 2-year project ARTEMIS that ran between November 2022 and October 2024 within the frame of the EJP SOIL project (Funding number, 862695). 12 project partners from 8 countries were brought together, addressing the following research aims:

1. Quantitatively summaries the current knowledge and outcomes on the contribution of soils to ecosystem services related to climate change mitigation and sustainable agricultural production in agroecological systems.
2. Improved knowledge on the resilience of specific agroecological systems to withstand climate extremes in comparison with commonly practiced controls.
3. Improved knowledge on how different management options for agroecological systems affect soil services.
4. Delivery of science-based practical knowledge on the sustainability of agroecological systems to practitioners.

The project used a diverse toolset of approaches for addressing these research questions, including literature meta-analyses, evaluation of long-term field data, laboratory experiments, numerical modelling and assessments in the field. This report brings thus together the main scientific outputs of the ARTEMIS project.

The report is composed of two major parts. Part one provides an overview and a synthesis of all research activities that were performed within ARTEMIS. Part two provides the detailed description of all research activities performed within ARTEMIS and consist of the actual working package deliverables.

EJP SOIL
ARTEMIS

Agro-ecological strategies for promoting climate change
Mitigation and Adaptation by enhancing soil ecosystem
services and sustainable crop production

Part 1: General project synthesis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695

Meta-analysis on soil ecosystem services in different agroecological systems (ARTEMIS WP4)

For evaluating the currently available knowledge on the effect of different agroecological practices on climate mitigation we performed literature meta-analyses to capture the available knowledge on a European scale. The implementation of organic farming systems claims to be more sustainable and environmentally friendly than conventional agriculture because of the enhancement of climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies. At same time, they also favor the resilience of agroecosystems against external biotic and abiotic stressors, by increasing biodiversity, soil quality, and the potential of water and carbon storage in soils. Nevertheless, organic farming systems are repeatedly reported to have lower average crop yields than conventional systems. Although several global meta-analyses on the performance of organic farming systems were conducted, they neither focused on cereal-based rotations, nor comprehensively identified the role of pedo-climatic factors and management practices on organic cereal yield specifically in Europe.

In a first meta-analysis, the cereal yield and temporal yield variation were analysed in organic and conventional farming systems on an European scale. The aims of this meta-analysis were (1) to quantitatively summarize existing knowledge and outcomes on yields and temporal yield variation of cereal-based rotations in organic farming systems compared to conventional systems across Europe; (2) to answer the question whether cereal-based organic farming systems do have lower average crop yields than conventional ones; (3) to identify strategies to reduce cereal yield gaps between organic and conventional farming systems and maintain the yield stability over time.

The collected database consists of 50 field experiments located in 15 European countries, covering nine European environmental zones, from Boreal to Mediterranean South. Cereal-based rotations were cultivated organically and conventionally on mineral soils during 3 – 35 years, and yields for winter rye, winter and spring wheat, spring barley and spring oats were annually measured. Organic farming systems relied either on animal-based, plant-based fertilizers, or both sources of N input. Conventional systems in most experiments received solely mineral fertilization. In most studies, fields in both farming systems were conventionally tilled and not irrigated.

Across all studies, yield in organic farming systems was about 30% lower compared to conventional agriculture. Nevertheless, yield gap between organic and conventional systems

was reduced with increasing N input in organic farming. Hence, doubling N inputs in organic systems compared to conventional ones, no yield gap was observed. Yield performance of organic systems varied statistically significantly across farming types ($p=0.021$), that was likely related to the different quality and quantity of N inputs added. A 20% of yield gap was observed in organic systems using animal-based fertilizers (animal manure, slurry or manure compost). A 35% of yield gap was shown in organic systems using only legumes or mixed green manure, however, the gap may be reduced to a 27% by keeping the number of crops in rotation as high as in conventional systems, but not exceeding it. Moreover, yield gap decreased with increasing average annual temperature ($p=0.002$), and, hence, with moving from Boreal and Nemoral environmental zones (40% yield gap) to Mediterranean South (no yield gap).

We suggested that yield gap for cereals may be reduced by increasing N input in organic systems, using animal manure, slurry and manure compost, and by better managing organic rotations relied on solely legumes or mixed green manure. Meta-analysis revealed that European studies poorly reported the quantity of N sources from green manure in the estimate of the N input to the organic systems. Thus, it is difficult to draw a conclusion whether the larger yield gap (35%) was caused by insufficient quantity of green manure, or its quality, such as high C/N ratio, and, thus, slow mineralization compared to animal manure.

A second meta-analysis was performed how organic farming do affect soil organic carbon concentrations in Europe, considering the high diversity in pedo-climatic factors. Conventional agriculture is often characterized by intensive management practices and therefore considered detrimental to soil health and more specifically, soil organic carbon (SOC). The latter plays a central role in the provision of several soil ecosystem services, such as climate change mitigation, water security or biodiversity conservation. Therefore, the transition of conventional farming systems to more sustainable production systems is more necessary than ever. Organic farming is a system, which is often perceived to have generally beneficial impacts on the environment compared to conventional farming as it promotes the resilience of agroecosystems, increases biodiversity, soil quality, and the potential of water storage. There is conflicting evidence on the effect of organic farming on SOC accrual, with research claiming for a beneficial effect impacts whereas others conclude that these effects are largely driven by organic fertilizer inputs rather than farming system types. Although there are global meta-analyses studying this effect available, they include a diverse range of agricultural systems and therefore are not focussed on arable systems with cereal-based rotations. Further, they are not

representative for European conditions and show weaknesses in meta-analytical methodology. Based on these limitations and knowledge gaps, the aim of this meta-analysis was (1) to quantitatively summarize existing knowledge and outcomes on SOC of cereal-based rotations in organic farming systems compared to conventional systems across Europe; (2) to answer the question whether cereal-based organic farming systems increase SOC compared to conventional ones and (3) to identify moderators impacting the result.

Findings showed that, compared to conventional systems which received solely mineral fertilizer, SOC in organic farming systems was larger, ranging from +4% to +19%. However, this effect did not become apparent when organic farming was compared to conventional systems receiving mineral plus organic fertilizer. Not differentiating between the different fertilization regimes in conventional systems resulted in only a small positive, but non-significant overall effect of organic farming on SOC, in comparison to conventional farming systems, across all 46 studies.

However, the positive effect of organic farming on SOC was enhanced with increasing mean annual precipitation, soil pH and clay contents and with expanding crop rotation duration of the organic systems. Other agricultural management practices applied did not have a significant impact on SOC changes due to organic agriculture. Therefore, transition of stockless conventional farms into organic farms seems to be beneficial in terms of SOC increase regardless of pedo-climatic conditions in Europe. However, after transition of conventional farms using the combination of mineral fertilizers and animal manure, slurry, and/or green manure, a positive SOC change cannot be necessarily expected in specific pedo-climatic conditions, such as arid climate, moderately acidic soils, or in soil with low clay content ($\leq 10\%$). In other words, local pedo-climatic conditions and fertilization of conventional farms need to be considered when intending to increase or stabilize SOC by shifting farming systems to organics.

Thirdly, also the effect of conservation agriculture and organic agriculture as a potential to reduce N₂O emissions was assessed. Given the lack of a sufficient number of studies to perform a meta-analysis on a European level, this was done in a narrative review. For that, 11 studies identified of being suitable for the conducted synthesis. The selected revealed contrasting effects of CA on N₂O emissions when compared to conventional agriculture. The impact varies since both relative emission reductions were observed ranging from 27% (Mutegi et al., 2010) to 84% (Garcia-Manco et al., 2016) but also stimulated emission were observed of 10% (Krauss

et al., 2017) to 620%, as observed by Bagg et al. (2003). Five studies found an emission reduction of which 3 were statistically significant: -27% by Mutegi et al. (2010), -52% by Chatskikh and Olesen (2007) and -84% by Garcia-Manco et al. (2016). Guardia et al. (2016) observed no impact of conservation agriculture. For the five studies observing emission stimulation, 3 were statistically significant, stimulations of 53% by Badagliacca et al. (2018), 56% by Sheehy et al. (2013) and 620% by Bagg et al. (2003) were observed. The strong significant impact on both emission reductions as well as on N₂O emission stimulations indicate that no uniform effect of conservation agriculture on N₂O emissions can be identified.

The findings on the effect of organic farming on SOC as well as the effects of organic farming and conservative agriculture on N₂O emissions are currently prepared for a submission in a peer-review journal jointly.

The outputs of these research activities are currently prepared for publication as two individual manuscripts for submission to a peer-reviewed journals. Drafts of the manuscripts are provided in the ARTEMIS project deliverable D4.1 and in part two of this report.

Identification of agroecological systems and soil properties that support yield stability, using long term field experiments (ARTEMIS WP2)

Long-term field experiments (LTEs) offer unique opportunities to assess the long-term effects of various cropping systems and management practices, particularly concerning time-dependent parameters such as yield stability. Indeed, these experiments provide long-term data and observations that allow for the analysis of yearly variability in crop performance under fluctuating environmental conditions.

The tasks T2.3 and T2.3 of the EJP SOIL “ARTEMIS” project aims to identify agroecosystems with increased yield stability and to deepen our understanding of how specific AE practices influence soil ecosystem service indicators driving yield stability.

To reach these objectives, the differences in yield and yield stability between AE and conventional farming systems, particularly regarding their resilience during periods of climatic stress, were evaluated in regionally representative field experiments across Europe. These experiments allow for context and system-specific analysis of data as the implementation of AE practices and their effects on soil properties are very often context specific.

Specifically, this research investigates the influences of panel of farming systems (conventional and organic), combined agroecological practices, soil and crop management practices including the management of crop rotations, crop protection, various tillage methods, organic/mineral fertilization, covering of the soil, incorporation of crop residues on yield levels and stability.

Seven long-term experiments (LTE)s managed by 6 partners institutions in four countries have been selected for the processing of the yield stability analyses in ARTEMIS project. These LTEs cover a diversified range of pedoclimatic areas of Europe. A south to north gradient was obtained with contrasted types of climates: mediterranean, continental and temperate.

Currently, there exists a list of 42 stability indices. As mentioned above, the selection of yield stability indices has to be specific to the LTEs since their characteristics and typical issues can vary a lot. At least the coefficient of variation (CV) was the minimal common stability indicator calculated by each partner. The CV normalizes the absolute variability of yield data (i.e., standard deviation (SD)) relative to the mean yield, so the CV is defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean. This indicator presents the advantage of being independent of

the unit in which the measurement was taken. Thus, this indicator can be used to compare data sets with different units or widely different means.

The results and conclusions drawn from the individual reports of the ARTEMIS project partners support the hypothesis that some agroecological practices have the potential to enhance the productivity and resilience of agroecosystems under climatic stress. However, it is important to acknowledge that these results are highly context-specific and occasionally contradictory at European scale, making it challenging to formulate general conclusions from these case-studies. Variations in pedoclimatic conditions across the sites, as well as the diverse types and implementation methods of soil and crop management practices, the category and species of agricultural crops (such as vegetables in MITIORG versus arable crops in the other LTEs), and the specifics of crop rotations, contribute to this complexity. Additionally, the duration of the LTEs is important, as treatment effects are expected to become more pronounced as the LTEs age.

Soil related drivers of yield stability and thus an evaluation of farming system performance with respect to the long-term performance was performed in detail at the Swiss DOK LTE, where organic and conventional farming systems are compared. Multivariate adaptive regression spline models (MARS) were used to identify non-linear relationships between environmental, agronomic, and management factors on yield fluctuations. Fertilization factors such as mineral nitrogen fertilization and the climate variables had a much larger effect on yields than soil properties had. Among soil properties, soil organic carbon (SOC) content provided the strongest explanation of yield variability for potatoes and maize with a significant positive effect on yields. In detail, crop yields of potatoes are predicted to increase with increasing soil organic carbon (SOC) concentrations until a threshold of 0.97 %. After that, increases in soil organic carbon concentrations did not affect yields any further. Since means of the observed farming system ranged between 1.1 and 1.26%, this threshold can be interpreted as critical limit, where soils with lower concentrations had significantly lower yields. For maize yields, a strict positive trend was observed after a threshold of 1.14 % of SOC. For winter wheat, total soil N content played the largest role for predicting yield after a minimum concentration of 0.139 %. Since soil N stocks could only be maintained over a period of 35 years in the organically managed systems with full fertilisation, the active management of also longer persisting soil properties such as soil N stocks seem both feasible and necessary for improve the system performance. At the same time, this initiates potential trade-off

situations, where decisions need to be made between the maintenance of soil N stock and potential N losses to other environmental compartments (Oberson et al., 2024).

The following articles resulted from the data analysis: Oberholzer, S., Herrmann, C., Bodenhausen, N., Krause, H. M., Mestrot, A., Speranza, C. I., & Jarosch, K. A. (2024). No effect on biological or chemical soil properties when amended with effective microorganisms for improved cover crop decomposition. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 197, 105358. Oberson, A., Jarosch, K. A., Frossard, E., Hammelehle, A., Fließbach, A., Mäder, P., & Mayer, J. (2024). Higher than expected: Nitrogen flows, budgets, and use efficiencies over 35 years of organic and conventional cropping. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 362, 108802. Oberholzer, S., Jarosch, K.A., Harder, N., Steffens, M., Speranza, C.I., (accepted), Cover cropping in organic reduced tillage systems: Maximizing soil cover or plant aboveground biomass input?, *European Journal of Soil Science*. Further, several Manuscripts on the effect of agroecological practices on yield variability and soil related properties on individual long term field experiments are currently under preparation. Draft manuscripts are provided in the ARTEMIS project deliverable D2.2 and D2.3.

Identification of best AE practices fostering soil health in a changing climate (ARTEMIS WP3)

For better understanding the effect of future climatic conditions on crop yields and soil properties, a numerical modelling approach was applied on one selected case study. In details, the process-based ARMOSA crop model was applied to evaluate the effects of two production systems (crop-production farms vs. livestock-production farms) and two agricultural management practices (conventional vs. organic) on soil C sequestration, nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions, nitrate (NO₃) leaching, and crop yields under both current and future climatic conditions (2040 - 2069 and 2070 - 2100) in northern Europe. This was done with a case study that was located in the South Savo region of Finland, in Mikkeli.

A five-year crop rotation was designed to reflect common agricultural practices in both conventional (C) and organic (O) systems in the region, representative of crop and livestock production farms. For crop production farms, the rotation included cereals such as spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), oats (*Avena sativa*), rye (*Secale cereale*), and spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), along with oilseed rape and meadow hay, with fodder pea included in organic rotations. Livestock farm rotations, instead, consisted of two years of cereals followed by three years of meadow hay, with fescue and timothy as the primary species, and clover incorporated in organic systems. Nine different scenarios were simulated, involving varying combinations of residue management strategies (retained or removed) and fertilization practices. Simulations were conducted using the ARMOSA process-based crop model (Perego et al., 2013), which has been already successfully used in Finland (Valkama et al., 2020). Three simulation scenarios were set up, one for the current climatic conditions (1999 - 2022), and two for future climate projections (2040 - 2069 and 2070 - 2100).

Results show that, under current conditions, organic rotations that incorporate perennial crops, crop residue, green manure, and stable carbon fertilizers demonstrated the highest sustainability, as indicated by the Σ ommit Index. These systems outperformed conventional ones in terms of both productivity and reduced environmental impacts. Conventional systems, particularly those without crop residue incorporation, exhibited the lowest sustainability.

Future climate scenarios predict a substantial decline in the sustainability of most systems, particularly those dominated by annual crops. This decline is driven by reduced yields, increased nitrogen losses, and accelerated soil carbon depletion, suggesting that current organic practices may be insufficient to meet the challenges posed by climate change. Exploring new

organic and conservation cropping systems will be essential to address these challenges effectively.

In parallel, to leverage results from a controlled phytotron experiment to assess soil microbial population dynamics in response to extreme soil temperature and moisture conditions under two climate change scenarios based on IPCC projections. The experimental data obtained will inform the development of response function curves necessary for integrating microbial dynamics into the ARMOSA model, thereby enhancing its ability to accurately simulate the impact of microbial processes on soil health, nutrient cycling, and carbon sequestration. While this integration is a complex and ongoing task, the findings presented in this report will provide a preliminary overview of expected microbial responses to extreme environmental conditions, establishing a crucial foundation for future model enhancements. Two different climatic change scenarios established according to IPCC simulations, taking as reference the climatic conditions of the eastern Po Valley in northern Italy as described in (Manici et al., 2016), were simulated using a ploughed soil under conventional crop rotation in central Po valley (Italy). After a preliminary experiment in which two extreme conditions (flooding and drought) were tested in the phytotron on wheat and maize (M41-M43 of the EJPSOIL) and the methodology to monitoring soil water content using suitable probes and remote data recording was set up, two final simulation cycles were planned. Wheat was adopted as target crop due to its better performance in the preliminary in phytotron simulation under extreme conditions.

Warm and cold spring temperature regimes were tested in phytotron with two subsequent cycles at three water content levels. After soil DNA extraction, the quantitative response of total fungi and bacteria were quantified using digital PCR as described in (Manici et al., 2024) and real-time PCR respectively as described in (Manici et al., 2022) and expressed in term of number of DNA copies per μl of soil DNA.

This DNA-based quantification of fungal and bacteria in soil allowed a more accurate evaluation of soil functioning variation in response to simulated climatic change as compared to conventional approaches to date used such chloroform fumigation-extraction (CFE) and substrate-induced respiration (SIR) (Semenov et al., 2018).

Results show that the simulation of the microbial biomass response to temperature and soil water content, the results confirm that, referring to the climatic conditions of the eastern Po Valley in northern Italy, the microbial biomass almost doubles in warm springs compared to those where the temperature trend is lower than the seasonal average. Furthermore, soil

microbial biomass is much more sensitive to prolonged dry periods than to prolonged wet periods.

The significant variation of the fungal/bacterial ratio in response to temperature suggests that changes in spring temperature may induce changes in soil functionality, however those changes should be considered as a microbiome variation trend in the long period. Indeed, as shown in this study, the fungal-to-bacterial ratio can vary significantly in the short term (60 days in this case), suggesting that the balance between soil fungi and bacteria varies continuously over the seasons. Considering that soil microbiome can vary according to soil type, climate and land use and that microorganisms have a variety of evolutionary adaptations and physiological acclimation mechanisms, it is very difficult to generalize the impact of climate change. Therefore, when modelling the microbial response to climatic changes, the main responses here obtained of the microbial biomass to changes in temperature and water content in spring soils must be considered.

Two manuscripts for submission to a peer-reviewed journal is currently in preparation. Draft manuscripts are provided in the ARTEMIS project deliverable D3.1.

Framework for an agroecological (lighthouse) farm network on soil quality and ecosystem services (ARTEMIS WP5)

While long term field experiments allow for a robust comparison of the impacts of different farming systems, they often use standardized management that is not necessarily representative and line with actual agricultural practice. This research activity thus specifically focuses on establishing a network of AE farms and developing a harmonised monitoring framework to evaluate the effects of AE practices on soil health and soil-related ecosystem services (ESS).

An agroecological farm network that has thus been established in collaboration with six project partners, representing various land uses, AE systems, and pedo-climatic conditions. The AE farm network served as a test case for the on-farm monitoring framework developed within ARTEMIS and has provided preliminary data on soil health indicators such as soil organic carbon (SOC), pH, and bulk density. The monitoring framework has proven effective for harmonised data collection across different countries, fostering collaboration among research partners. Preliminary results have indicated a high variability in soil indicators across the various sites, underscoring the challenges inherent in on-farm research due to the diversity of conditions

In the frame of ARTEMIS, we conducted preliminary testing of the soil health monitoring framework and the established database within the AE farm network. Due to time constraints and limited data availability, preliminary data analysis faced challenges: not all sites were represented, and several soil parameters were missing. The preliminary data analysis focused, therefore, on soil health indicators with more than 20 data points in the topsoil, along with corresponding texture data. This allowed us to include soil organic carbon (SOC), total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (P), potassium (K), pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and electrical conductivity (EC) in our analysis. The preliminary analysis compared AE fields with reference fields (where available) that lacked AE-specific treatments. We utilized a straightforward multivariate model that incorporated soil texture prior to evaluating system effects. This assessment was conducted using a hierarchical linear model (Type I Error), represented by the equation $y = \text{clay} + \text{sand} + \text{system}$. In this context, y refers to the soil health indicator being measured, while the term "system" signifies the comparison between AE fields and reference plots.

The analysis showed no significant differences between the AE field and the reference field for any of the tested soil health variables. The soil health indicators displayed considerable

variability among the AE farms across six different partner countries, underscoring the importance of interpreting results within their specific pedo-climatic contexts. In the preliminary analysis, we only accounted for soil texture, which was for several of the tested soil health indicators a significant driver. By incorporating additional environmental variables, such as mean annual temperature and mean annual precipitation, we could potentially reduce the masking effect of environmental variability further and better reveal the effects of AE on soil health (Walder et al., 2023). Further analysis will be necessary once more comprehensive data, including these environmental parameters, become available.

Future efforts should prioritize expanding and refining the farm network to more effectively evaluate the impact of AE systems across varying environments. For instance, more targeted monitoring should focus on specific land uses and aim to evaluate the same or similar crop types wherever feasible consistently. This approach would allow for more accurate comparisons of AE management effects, providing insights into how these practices perform in different soil types, climates, and agricultural contexts.

To thoroughly assess the impact of AE systems on soil health and ESS across Europe, it is necessary to expand the AE farm network, increase the number of farms, and focus on specific land uses and similar crops to promote meaningful comparisons. By incorporating additional farms and utilising the comprehensive monitoring framework and database, future research can provide more tailored AE solutions that address local needs and regional preferences. This approach will ultimately contribute to the development of more sustainable and resilient agricultural systems throughout Europe.

Report details are provided in the ARTEMIS project deliverables D5.1 and D5.2.

Agro-ecological strategies for promoting climate change
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Part 2: Scientific Project Deliverables

Scientific project deliverables are currently still subject to an embargo, since the related scientific articles are currently in the process of being prepared for publication to peer-reviewed journals. Interested parties may contact the project leader for more detailed information.